

WHO WAS TOLE-BEY?

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During the holidays with a group of colleagues, we went to the city of Tashkent in order to visit the holy shrines and other entertainment venues. During our trip, we witnessed an ancient sanctuary located on Abdulla Qadiri Street in the city center, constantly attracting the attention of those who visited the capital. It turns out that the great public figure and poet, a man known among the local population as "Swallow-biy", was actually a Kazakh public figure, poet and commander Tolebi Alibekuli.

In order to know more about this great man, we questioned local residents to get even more information, searched on Internet sites, turned to a number of resources and found out the following for ourselves!

"Tale-biy" was born in 1663 near the pasture of Jaysan in the same district of the Zhambyl region of Kazakhstan. He was a descendant of the great Zhuz and was a statesman and an incredibly strong eloquent man. He was also very popular

among the people as the most righteous and truthful judge.

During the invasion of the Kalmyks at the end of the 17th century, all the locals left their homes and places and left an egg in vati, it turned out that only the Kazakh statesman Tolebiy did not leave his country. At that time, when the captain of the army "Kalmyks" asked to comment on his work, he informed the land of fate that Swallow had built a new house, that he could not break it and that he loved the place of his birth very much. After this incident, Captain Kalmykov Tolebi admired his intelligence and ordered him to stay alive, and among the local population he received the nickname "Swallow-biy".

Tolebiy was a supporter of the unification of all Kazakh zhuzes, a single Kazakh Khanate and the formation of a centralized government. To this end, he

supported the reforms of Tauke Khan and carried out several effective works to strengthen cooperation with neighboring countries. He also showed enthusiasm in the fight against the Kalmyks on the way to unite the Kazakh people around the upper Zhouz. Much better known as a skilful commander, Tolebi developed a set of laws "Jeti Jar" (*seven statutes*), combining the experience and knowledge that he acquired during his

life, which over the years have gained great importance in public administration. Tolebiy died in 1756 at the age of 93 in AK-Burkhan Ovul, near the Langer district (*now Tolebiy district of Turkestan region*) in the Southern region of Kazakhstan, and was buried in Tashkent. A monument was erected on his grave, a mausoleum was built, which has survived to this day. Despite the fact that the past years have damaged the appearance of the mausoleum, thanks to independence, it was restored again and formed as one of the most beautiful shrines.

Currently, Tole-biy is remembered among Kazakhstanis as a person deserving of deep respect and attention, districts in the Jambyl and Turkestan regions of Kazakhstan, in other regions ovals and streets are named after him.

The famous poet, who was born in the village of Tuzel, Kibray district, Tashkent region, and Mekembai Umarali wrote an epic about the life of the Kazakh Tribe called "The Fox-Swallow".

This shrine and its surroundings are landscaped by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the administration of the city of Tashkent and attract tourists. At the same time, delegations consisting of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan and representatives of the Government will definitely visit the Talebiy sanctuary during their visit to Tashkent. The last time Kassym-Jomart Tokayev visited the Tole-biy sanctuary was during his visit to Tashkent on December 22, 2022.

At the end of my speech, I would like to note that public figures, poets, military leaders and eloquent people, such as "Tole-biy", have always been glorified by the people, and we have once again witnessed that the rich legacy left by them is priceless for our great history.

